

Distribution and nature of soil that suppresses rice sheath blight (ShB) in the Philippines

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ShB is caused by an aerial form of *Rhizoctonia solani* Kuhn and occurs worldwide in rice under varying cultivation. To study soil that suppresses ShB, we collected rhizosphere soil samples at heading stage in 1990 wet season from various types of ricefields at the IRRI experimental farm and at 12 other sites in the Philippines (Table 1).

We used a cork borer to make a 5-mm disc of *R. solani* mycelia from a day-old culture on potato dextrose agar. A stereomicroscope was used to record linear mycelial growth on the soil surface every 48 h for 4 d.

About 44% of the 99 soil samples suppressed *R. solani*. The rest were conducive soils. Thirty-two percent of the 65 soil samples from the IRRI experimental farm were suppressive. Linear growth of *R. solani* on the suppressive soils was about 50% or less of that on the conducive soils. This means ShB severity was less in suppressive than in conducive soils. Samples from disease-free and relatively ShB-free lowland fields appeared to be more suppressive of *R. solani*.

Table 1. Distribution of soils suppressive of or conducive to *Rhizoctonia solani* in the Philippines. IRRI, 1990 wet season.

Location	Total (no.)	Suppressive (no.)	Conductive (no.)
IRRI	65	21	44
Cavite	8	5	3
Albay	6	6	0
Camarines Sur	6	5	1
Legaspi City	2	2	0
Laguna	3	1	2
Victoria, Laguna	3	2	1
Paagahan	1	1	0
Sta. Cruz, Laguna	1	0	1
Camarines	1	0	1
Bay (Aplaya), Laguna	1	0	1
Calauan, Laguna	1	0	1
Masiit (Hoechst), Laguna	1	0	1
Total	99	43	56

Table 2. Correlation of soil properties and inhibitory effect of suppressive soil. ^a IRRI, 1990 wet season.

Factor	Data range	Average	R ²	F	Regression equation ^b
pH	4.85 - 7.72	6.45	0.34**	20.25**	Y = 44.41 - 4.43X (pH)
K ⁺	4.30 - 21.70	11.51	0.12*	5.48*	Y = 9.60 + 0.54X (K ⁺)
Ca ²⁺	38.00-124.00	89.81	0.09*	3.83*	Y = 5.66 + 0.11X (Ca ²⁺)
TEB	23.00 - 42.00	31.41	0.10*	4.25*	Y = 2.61 + 0.42X (TEB)
CEC	16.00 - 48.00	31.48	0*	0*	Y = 15.60 + 0.007X (CEC)

^a * = significant at 0.05 level. ** = significant at 0.01 level. ^b Y = mycelial length (mm/d); n = 42; the 42 soil samples were from IRRI experimental farm plots A, B, C, L, M, N, and 116-1002.

Sterilization nullified the inhibitory effect. But it could be restored in a mixture with 20% suppressive soil. Abiotic factors such as Ca²⁺, K⁺, CEC, TEB, and pH were significantly

correlated with the inhibitory effect of the suppressive soil (Table 2). It appears that soil microorganisms and some abiotic factors were associated with the suppressive effect of the soils. □

Brevennia rehi Lindinger, vector for the sheath rot (ShR) pathogen

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We attempted to establish the role of rice mealybug *Brevennia rehi* Lindinger in spreading ShR caused by *Sarocladium oryzae* (Sawada) W. Gams & D. Hawksw.

We collected rice mealybugs from ShR-infested fields. IR20 was inoculated using a camel's hair brush to place three bugs/sheath enclosing the young panicles. Controls were inoculated with mealybugs mass-reared in the laboratory.

Mealybugs were collected from ShR-infested sheaths, soaked in 25 ml of sterile, distilled water, and then shaken for 30 min using an electric shaker. One drop of the suspension was

microscopically examined. Mealybugs from the diseased tissues were also placed directly on potato dextrose agar medium that had been surface sterilized with 10% sodium hypochlorite for 5 min. They were then incubated at 28 ± 2 °C.

Seventy-two percent of the plants inoculated with field-collected mealybugs exhibited typical ShR symptoms within 15 d. Plants inoculated with laboratory-reared mealybugs did not produce any symptoms.

Critical examination of mealybugs collected from the diseased sheaths revealed that *S. oryzae* conidia were present on the body surface (1150 conidia/ml of water) as well as internally. Plants inoculated with the internal ShR pathogen through pin pricks inside the boot leaf exhibited ShR symptoms within 25 d. This shows that mealybugs have an important role in the spread of the ShR pathogen. □

Detection of the Philippine isolate of rice yellow dwarf (RYD) agent using DNA probes

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RYD is a serious rice disease caused by a mycoplasma-like organism (MLO). DNA probes pRYD-12 (may be chromosomal in origin) and pRYD-19 (may be extrachromosomal in origin) for RYD

MLO DNA were developed in Japan to diagnose RYD. We tested whether these two probes can detect a Philippine isolate of RYD.

DNA was extracted by homogenizing 0.1 g infected tissue in 0.9 ml 2X CTAB buffer (2% wt/vol cetyl trimethylammonium bromide, 100 mM tris-HCL, pH 8.0, 1.4 M NaCl, 20 mM Na₂ EDTA) that contained 2 μl 2-mercaptoethanol. The homogenate (0.5 ml) was incubated at 65 °C for 30 min and centrifuged at 15,000 rpm for 15 s.

Detection of DNA of rice yellow dwarf MLO in rice leaves using DNA probes, pRYD-19 and pRYD-12. J = Japanese isolate, P = Philippine isolate, H = healthy. Numerals = weight of fresh leaves per dot.

Supernatant was recovered and DNA reextracted from the pellet by adding 0.3 ml 1X CTAB buffer, mixing well, incubating at 65 °C for 10 min, and centrifuging at 15,000 rpm for 5 min. Supernatants were pooled together and extracted with an equal volume of chloroform-isoamyl alcohol (24:1). The supernatant was recovered and 0.7 volume of isopropanol (-20 °C) was added and mixed well. The mixture was left for 10 min at room temperature, then centrifuged as before.

The DNA pellet was dissolved in TE buffer (10 mM tris-HCl, pH 8.0, 1 mM Na₂ EDTA). The same amount of healthy tissue was processed as a control. The DNA extract of the Japanese RYD isolate was also included in the tests for comparison.

Twofold serial dilutions of the DNA preparations were spotted onto nylon membranes (Hybond N+, Amersham). The enhanced chemiluminescence method (ECL Gene Detection System, Amersham) was used for probe labeling with peroxidase, hybridization, and detection of signal.

Both DNA probes hybridized with Philippine RYD MLO DNA (see figure). We were able to detect Philippine RYD MLO DNA in a minimum of 60 µg of

rice tissue with these probes. The Philippine isolate gave slightly weaker signal than the Japanese isolate in both probes. Moreover, pRYD-19 showed stronger hybridization signal with the Philippine isolate than did pRYD-12.

Healthy extracts gave a negative reaction. Results showed that DNA probes developed for Japanese isolates of RYD can be used to detect Philippine RYD isolates. □

Variants of rice grassy stunt virus (RGSV) in the Philippines

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RGSV sources maintained on Taichung Native 1 (TN1) in an IRRI greenhouse showed varied symptoms. We conducted this study to clarify the nature of these variable RGSV symptoms.

Greenhouse isolates and field-collected plants with typical RGSV symptoms were tested for their reactions to antisera to known viruses that infect rice in the Philippines. The samples reacted only to the anti-RGSV sera.

Four distinct symptomatologic RGSV variants were obtained after several RGSV transfers to TN1 by a colony of brown planthoppers (BPH). Isolates were

designated as M3, M2, SC, and S2. M3 induced very mild symptoms where the infected plant sometimes looked like a healthy one. M2 caused moderately mild symptoms showing slightly stunted, less profuse, erect tillers, and slightly yellowed leaves. SC induced moderately severe symptoms with stunted growth, profuse spreading tillers, and narrow leaves with rusty necrotic spots. The very severe type, S2, induced severe stunting, greatly reduced number of tillers, and narrow leaves with mottling and necrotic spot (see table).

Transmission efficiency also varied. Isolate M2 was transmitted by a higher percentage of the BPH population. The incubation period in TN1 plants was longest in M3 (26 d), followed by M2 (22 d), SC (14 d), and S2 (11 d). Isolates M3 and M2 required longer periods (11 d and 9 d, respectively) before the vector became infective compared with SC and S2 (7 d) (see table).

Characteristics of 4 RGSV isolates.^a

	RGSV isolates			
	M3	M2	SC	S2
<i>Symptomatology^b</i>				
Plant height (cm)	53.2 b	48.3 b	40.5 c	36.4 a
Tiller type	Normal	Less profuse Erect type	Profuse tiller Spreading type	Less profuse spreading type
Leaf size	Normal	Slightly narrowed	Narrowed	Narrowed
Leaf color	Normal	Slightly yellowed	Pale green with rusty necrotic spot	Yellowing with mottling and necrotic spot
<i>Insect transmission^b</i>				
Active transmitter (%)	0-2.6	9.2-15.3	5.0-9.0	1.7-8.0
Incubation period in plant (d)	26 a	22 a	14 b	11 b
Incubation period in insect (d)	11 a	9 a	7 b	7 b
<i>Plant infection rate^c</i>				
TN1	17/178 (R) ay	173/250 (S) abx	105/148 (S) ax	75/231 (M) ax
IR42	8/216 (R) az	106/140 (S) ax	96/188 (M) ay	46/165 (R) aby
IR54	4/312 (R) ay	170/257 (S) abx	71/148 (M) ax	32/164 (R) aby
<i>Oryza nivara</i>	19/215 (R) ay	214/282 (S) abx	77/139 (M) ax	7/102 (R) by

^aR = resistant, S = susceptible, M = moderately susceptible. ^bTN1 plants at 3-4 wk after inoculation. In a row, means having a common letter are not significantly different at the 5% level. ^cNumbers before the slant bar indicate infected plants; those after the slant bar, the total number of plants. Means having a common letter in columns (abc) and in rows (xyz) are not significantly different at the 1 and 5% levels, respectively, by DMRT.